

README: Crowd-Grid & Recent Heat Packs

ATTENTION: This is a prototype. The information in this product is high-quality and has been subject to a rigorous quality assurance process. However, the form of the product and how it is published are subject to change.

This document provides an outline of the Crowd-Grid gridded dataset and associated Recent Heat Packs, specifically:

1. **What is Crowd-Grid?**
2. **What are the Recent Heat Packs?**
3. **How are the data structured?**
4. **How do I read the data?**
5. **How was the dataset built?**
6. **What can the information be used for?**
7. **How should I interpret the Crowd-Grid data?**
8. **How should I interpret the information in the Recent Heat Packs?**
9. **Further Resources & Acknowledgements**
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1. What is Crowd-Grid?

A recent Met Office project (2024-2025), funded by UK government through the [Hadley Centre Climate Programme](#), has built a new 1km gridded dataset (Crowd-Grid) for the UK of daily minimum and maximum temperatures spanning the period 01/01/2013 to 31/12/2024.

[Crowd-Grid](#) combines Met Office, crowdsourced, and third-party observations to give a detailed view of the temperatures people experience, including in built-up areas. It comprises a set of daily gridded maximum/minimum temperatures for 1x1km cells covering the entire UK. Each grid cell provides an estimate of the maximum/minimum temperature in the cell on that day. These estimates are based upon information derived from the relationship between point observations and a set of covariates (including spatial variation, elevation, proximity to the coast, and urban fraction).

Crowd-Grid differs from and complements the “standard” UK gridded dataset, [HadUK-Grid](#), that the Met Office also provides. HadUK-Grid constitutes the official long-term climatological record for the UK, providing a range of variables including temperature, precipitation, sunshine duration, and humidity from 1836 to present. HadUK-Grid uses the Met Office’s network of calibrated instruments from [standard observing sites](#) to provide the UK’s official record of temperature. To keep consistency throughout the long time series it is typically representative of grassy fields and parks.

Crowd-Grid portrays the temperatures we experience across a wider range of local environments than HadUK-Grid – not just grassy fields and parks, but also gardens, streets, and industrial estates. Each value in Crowd-Grid has to represent the greater variety of temperatures experienced across these settings. In this sense, the uncertainty in Crowd-Grid is larger than in HadUK-Grid.

2. What are the Recent Heat Packs?

A gridded dataset, while useful to some, will remain inaccessible to many. Therefore, a set of [Recent Heat Packs](#) have been developed that extract information from Crowd-Grid and make it available in a more accessible form. These "Recent Heat Packs" provide for each of the 393 UK local authorities:

- a 2-page Recent Heat Factsheet, which complements the 9-page Climate Report in the [Local Authority Climate Service](#) (LACS)
- three .csv files that provide the underlying data for the local authority and its constituent census areas: MSOAs in England and Wales, Intermediate Zones in Scotland, and District Electoral Areas in Northern Ireland

These packs have been designed to complement the [Local Authority Climate Service](#) (LACS), which provides considerable information about future climate. They provide additional information about recent local heat to complement the model-based projections in the LACS, for each of the 393 UK local authorities covered in the current beta version of the LACS. In addition, the Recent Heat Packs provide sub-local authority level information at census area level.

The envisaged beneficiaries include anyone working to build resilience to extreme heat, in particular. The intention is to support the identification of the areas and communities at greatest risk to high temperatures and pave the way for data-driven measures to adapt to current and future climates.

3. How are the data structured?

The data are organised as follows:

```
crowd-grid/  
├── v1.0/  
│   ├── 1km/  
│   │   ├── tasmax/  
│   │   │   ├── v20251219/  
│   │   │   │   ├── 2020/  
│   │   │   │   │   ├── 08/  
│   │   │   │   │   │   ├── daily-maximum-temperature_crowd-grid_20200806.nc  
│   │   │   ├── tasmin/  
│   │   │   │   ├── v20251219/  
│   │   │   │   │   ├── 2020/  
│   │   │   │   │   │   ├── 08/  
│   │   │   │   │   │   │   ├── daily-minimum-temperature_crowd-grid_20200806.nc  
recent-heat-packs/  
├── v1.0/  
│   ├── factsheets/  
│   │   ├── brighton-and-hove_recent-heat-pack_factsheet.pdf  
│   ├── metric-csvs/  
│   │   ├── brighton-and-hove_recent-heat-pack_metrics.csv
```

```
└─daily-csvs/
  └─brighton-and-hove_recent-heat-pack_daily-minimum-temperature.csv
  └─brighton-and-hove_recent-heat-pack_daily-maximum-temperature.csv
└─shapefiles/
  └─uk-local-authority-boundaries/
  └─uk-msoa-iz-dez-boundaries/
```

4. How do I read the data?

4.1 Crowd-Grid Gridded Data

Crowd-Grid gridded data are provided in NetCDF format. For details on the NetCDF standard, see:

- [Climate and Forecasts \(CF\) Metadata conventions for NetCDF](#)
- [NetCDF web site at Unidata](#)

The files provide a matrix of dimension 900 cells in x and 1450 cells in y, covering the whole of the UK at 1km resolution using OSGB36 projected coordinates.

Several libraries support the parsing of NetCDF data, including but not limited to:

- [iris](#)
- [xarray](#)
- [netcdf4](#)
- [gdal](#)

4.2 Recent Heat Packs

The .csv files may be imported into office spreadsheet software. The first row contains column headers. The columns are:

- **Date** (for daily data) or **Metric** (for annual mean metrics)
- the second column has values for the local authority area as a whole
- the remaining columns have values for the census areas within that local authority area

The .csv files may also be imported into GIS software. The column headers are area names that correspond to areas in the supplied shapefile.

5. How was the dataset built?

5.1 Crowd-Grid Gridded Data

5.1.1 Input observations data

The underpinning observations dataset comprises three sources: the Met Office's existing [land observation network](#), crowd-sourced weather observations uploaded to the Met Office's Weather Observations Website ([WOW](#)), and contributions from roadside networks operated by the UK's highways agencies (National Highways, Transport Scotland, and DfI NI).

5.1.2 Quality Control

The raw observations were aggregated to daily minimum and maximum temperatures. They were subsequently quality controlled using TITAN (Båserud et al., 2020), an open-source quality control software developed by the Norwegian Meteorological Institute specifically for crowdsourced observations.

Båserud, L., Lussana, C., Nipen, T. N., Seierstad, I. A., Oram, L., and Aspelien, T.: TITAN automatic spatial quality control of meteorological in-situ observations, *Adv. Sci. Res.*, 17, 153–163, doi:[10.5194/asr-17-153-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/asr-17-153-2020), 2020.

5.1.3 Gridding Method

The gridded dataset was built using Climate Grid, software developed and maintained by the Met Office's National Climate Information Centre (NCIC). This is the same software as is used in the generation of HadUK-Grid. Some adjustments to the HadUK-Grid configuration are made to account for differences in the spatial characteristics of crowdsourced and third-party networks. For further details regarding parameter selection, see [Mitchell & Fry \(2024\)](#).

5.2 Recent Heat Packs

The Recent Heat Packs were built entirely from Crowd-Grid (2013-2024). The metrics were calculated at 1km grid-box level and then averaged over the local authority and census area shapes.

6. What can the information be used for?

6.1 Use as a snapshot of recent climate

Crowd-Grid and the Recent Heat Factsheets provide a snapshot of the heat (and cold) experienced locally and recently (2013-2024) in the UK. We experienced this recent climate partly because of climate change and partly because of natural variability. The climate we experience varies naturally from decade to decade, and within the changed world we inhabit, we could have experienced different amount of heat across the UK and in individual areas.

As a snapshot of recent heat, we suggest a number of practical uses:

- The Recent Heat Factsheets may be used as part of a wider briefing about climate, or for raising awareness about extreme heat. They provide a snapshot of the heat that people have experienced recently. They give an indication of the current climate to which we need to be adapted already.
- The .csv files that supplement the Recent Heat Factsheets may be used to support adaptation to extreme heat. For example, they may contribute to risk assessments that compare the risks of extreme heat to people, buildings or assets in different parts of a local area. The .csv files provide temperature information for census areas (see below). It is legitimate to combine that information with census-based information about exposure and vulnerability to assess relative risk across a local area. It is likely that the areas that have experienced the hottest temperatures in the recent past will also experience them in the future, unless changes to the local environment alter the pattern of heat.
- The information may be used to complement the Climate Reports available through the Local Authority Climate Service. The Climate Reports provide projections of changes in

local temperature metrics under various levels of global warming, and for various future periods. These metrics include measures of extreme heat, such as Tropical Nights (see below). The Recent Heat Factsheets provide the same metrics for the recent past. These may be used to put those future projections into the context of lived experience. For example, the Climate Report shows the projected change in a metric from 1981-2000 (when global warming was 0.6°C) to a 2°C warmer world. The Recent Heat Factsheet shows the metric experienced recently in 2013-2024 (when global warming was 1.2°C).

6.2 Can the data be used to detect climate change?

The Crowd-Grid dataset and Recent Heat Packs only cover a relatively short period (2013-2024) that is insufficient to detect climate change. Therefore, fitting trends is not meaningful. We recommend instead that this period is treated as a snapshot of recent climate. This is the approach we have taken in the Recent Heat Factsheets.

For a longer record of local climate in the UK we recommend [HadUK-Grid](#). This complementary dataset covers a much longer period and is based on a network of standard long-term observing stations that uses calibrated equipment and is relatively consistent in its siting and spatial coverage. It is used by the Met Office for UK climate monitoring statistics.

For an assessment of how recent climate fits into the longer-term record, we recommend the series of [State of the UK Climate](#) reports.

7. How should I interpret the Crowd-Grid data?

By integrating crowdsourced and third-party observations from non-standard exposures, the Crowd-Grid dataset provides insight into the temperatures people experience in their day-to-day lives - particularly within suburban and urban areas. When viewed as a whole, they provide a snapshot of the heat and cold experienced in recent years (2013-2024).

We experienced this recent climate partly because of climate change - global warming in this period was 1.2C compared to pre-industrial - and partly because of natural variability. The climate we experience varies naturally from decade to decade, and within the changed world we inhabit, we could have experienced different amount of heat across the UK and in individual areas.

7.1 How do the temperatures in Crowd-Grid align with HadUK-Grid?

Crowd-Grid has been designed to differ from and complement the official UK climatological record, HadUK-Grid, that the Met Office also provides.

Due to differences in their underpinning datasets, the temperatures in Crowd-Grid show some differences to those in HadUK-Grid. Averaged across 2013-2024, Crowd-Grid is 0.17°C warmer than HadUK-Grid. There is a degree of seasonality to this average, with Crowd-Grid being 0.21°C warmer than HadUK-Grid across summer months (JJA), compared to 0.12°C warmer than HadUK-Grid across winter months (DJF). On any given day, there will be spatial variations between the two datasets, attributable to both the underpinning observations and the particular synoptic conditions on that day.

For daily maximum temperature, Crowd-Grid is almost the same as HadUK-Grid over the year as a whole and over the UK as a whole (Crowd-Grid is 0.058°C warmer), but there are larger differences

locally, particularly in summer. For daily minimum temperature, Crowd-Grid is a little warmer (0.275°C) over the year as a whole and over the UK as a whole. The crowdsourced observations used in Crowd-Grid are often closer to the built environment than Met Office sites, which may be why Crowd-Grid is a little warmer at night and - locally in summer - hotter by day.

We can place the differences between Crowd-Grid and HadUK-Grid into context by comparing them to the change in HadUK-Grid between 1981-2000 to 2013-2024. Over the UK as a whole, the changes from 1981-2000 to 2013-2024 are much larger than those differences. The annual mean temperature increased from 8.7°C to 9.52°C over that period, and Crowd-Grid only increased the latter number to 9.68°C. However, the difference between Crowd-Grid and HadUK-Grid can be relatively large locally. Crowd-Grid has the advantage of a denser network of observations; therefore, it is able to represent local variability in climate with more spatial detail than HadUK-Grid.

The data from Crowd-Grid are *complementary* to other official records provided by the Met Office. [HadUK-Grid](#) remains the standard dataset that constitutes the UK's official record of temperature, based upon observations from the Met Office's network of calibrated instruments from standard observing sites.

Finally, as a result of the non-standardised nature of crowdsourced and third-party observations, the uncertainty in Crowd-Grid is larger than in HadUK-Grid.

7.2 Examples

Crowd-Grid adds to our understanding of how local temperatures are influenced by the local setting - whether that is the urban/rural contrast, land cover, or topography. It achieves this in two ways.

1. By increasing the density of the observation network, so that more local climate variations are captured, whatever their cause.
2. By broadening the range of local environments that are sampled, so that a large city like London is represented by sites in built-up areas, as well as by Met Office sites in parkland like St James Park or Kew Gardens.

The gain in understanding offered by Crowd-Grid may best be illustrated by some examples from days and nights of extreme heat. In each case the figure shows the temperatures at Met Office sites (bold circles) and crowdsourced and 3rd party sites (thin circles). These are overlaid on the gridded temperatures for HadUK-Grid and Crowd-Grid.

On 19th July 2022 the UK reached 40°C for the first time. The night before was also exceptionally hot, and the UK record for daily minimum temperature was broken, reaching 26.8°C at a Met Office station at Shirburn Model Farm in Oxfordshire. The greatest heat that night was relatively localised. It would be unrealistic to expect to observe every hotspot using only the official Met Office sites (bold circles). But the additional observations (thin circles) have allowed Crowd-Grid to identify areas of heat like this one in Brighton, that would have otherwise escaped notice.

Figure 1 – Daily minimum temperature in and around Brighton, 19th July 2022.

July 20th, 2016, was another exceptionally hot night. The minimum temperatures at Met Office sites in London included St James Park (22.2°C) and Heathrow (22.3°C). The crowdsourced sites show that much larger parts of western London also remained above 22°C. The spatial coherence of these observations allows Crowd-Grid to represent that larger area of extreme heat.

Figure 2 – Daily minimum temperature in Greater London, 20th July 2016.

12th August 2020 was an exceptionally hot day, currently the 11th hottest in Central England Temperature (32.0°C). One of the areas of highest heat was in the lower Severn valley, around Gloucester and Cheltenham. There was no report from a Met Office site that observed this. The crowdsourced site network is spatially denser and so Crowd-Grid can represent this localised area of extreme heat.

Figure 3 – Daily maximum temperature in the Severn Valley, 12th August 2020.

7.3 What do the minimum/maximum temperatures represent?

Conventionally, observations of daily maximum and minimum temperature for a given day, “D,” represent the highest and lowest temperatures observed between 0900Z D and 0900Z D+1.

For HadUK-Grid, the Met Office subsequently assigns the grids according to the calendar day in which the maxima/minima occurred. Thus, in HadUK-Grid, the maximum temperature grid labelled as day D is derived from observations over the period 0900Z D to 0900Z D+1, whilst the minimum temperature grid labelled as day D is derived from observations over the period 0900Z D-1 to 0900Z D.

To maintain consistency with HadUK-Grid, Crowd-Grid also uses this calendar day convention. So, for example, the gridded daily minimum temperature for December 25th is the minimum observed from 0900Z on December 24th to 0900Z on December 25th. The gridded daily maximum temperature for December 25th is the maximum observed from 0900Z on December 25th to 0900Z on December 26th.

7.4 How do I calculate daily mean temperature from Crowd-Grid data?

For climatological purposes, the daily mean temperature (*tas*) is taken as the midpoint of the daily minimum (*tasmin*) and maximum (*tasmax*) temperatures:

$$tas = (tasmax + tasmin) / 2$$

To calculate a daily mean temperature for day “D” from Crowd-Grid data for comparison with HadUK-Grid:

Take the midpoint of the daily minimum and maximum temperatures for day labelled “D”.

For example, a daily mean temperature grid for 2022-07-19 aligned to HadUK-Grid should be calculated using the daily minimum grid `daily-minimum-temperature_crowd-grid_20220719.nc` and the daily maximum grid `daily-maximum-temperature_crowd-grid_20220719.nc`

In practice, this means that daily mean temperature is optimally calculated for day D (0000Z-2359Z) since daily minimum temperature is most likely to have occurred in the early hours of day D and daily maximum temperature is most likely to have occurred during day D.

8. How should I interpret the information in the Recent Heat Packs?

8.1 What are these metrics?

The metrics in the Recent Heat Packs include all the temperature metrics in the [Local Authority Climate Service](#) for more information about these. In addition, the Recent Heat Packs provide:

- **The 8th warmest night each year:** This metric is useful for building design. The following explanation is courtesy of DESNZ: In the proposed TM59 overheating criteria from the Chartered Institute of Building Services Engineers (CIBSE, 2025), Criterion b requires that at most seven nights between May and September may have a predicted mean temperature during occupied hours greater than 26°C (Cat.I dwellings) or 27°C (Cat.II dwellings). The human thermo-physical impact of heat on sleep, and the derivation of Criterion b using the EFUS dataset, is explained in Lomas and Li (2023). Criterion b in TM59 (CIBSE 2025) limits exceedance of the bedroom temperature threshold (either 26°C or 27°C) to seven nights. Thus, if the mean temperature on the 8th warmest night exceeds the threshold value Criterion b is failed, otherwise Criterion b is passed. The metric supplied by this Data Summary Product is not the temperature inside buildings but rather the local ambient temperature outside. While this does not tell us if we have exceeded the criterion, it does indicate whether it would be more or less difficult to cool a home by natural ventilation on that 8th warmest night.
- **Warm Nights:** the number of nights over 15°C each year. This complements "Tropical Nights", which is the number of nights over 20°C each year. This 15°C metric is included because 20°C nights are rare in many areas of the UK in the present climate. The spatial pattern of the 15°C metric gives an indication of the spatial pattern of the 20°C Tropical Nights that more areas of the UK may experience in the future under climate change.
- **Heatwave metrics:** the average number of heatwaves experienced each year, and the average length of those heatwaves. A heatwave is deemed to occur when there are 3 or more successive days where the maximum temperature exceeds a particular threshold. That threshold varies across the UK, from 25°C to 28°C. The Met Office map of thresholds has [evolved](#) over the time covered by this dataset. The thresholds used in this Data Summary Product are similar to the current (2022) version, but rather than being consistent across a ceremonial county, these are consistent across each highest-level local authority for the recent administrative geography for the UK (e.g. consistent across Liverpool City Region, which includes parts of the ceremonial county of Cheshire).

CIBSE (2025) TM59: Overheating risk in dwellings: a design stage methodology. Chartered Institution of Building Services Engineers, London. (Under development)

Lomas KJ and Li M (2023) An overheating criterion for bedrooms in temperate climates: Derivation and application. Building Services Engineering Research and Technology, Vol.44, Iss.5, p. 485-517 (2023). doi:[10.1177/01436244231183113](https://doi.org/10.1177/01436244231183113)

8.2 What was the Global Warming Level?

The Local Authority Climate Service (LACS) provides information about local climate using Global Warming Levels (GWLs). For example, it provided information for the 2001-2020 (1°C) period and the 1.5°C future period. These GWLs are the amount of global warming since pre-industrial (1850-1990 - see the LACS [Scientific Detail](#)). The information in the Recent Heat Factsheet is based on what was observed in 2013-2024, when the GWL was 1.2°C. This calculation matches the LACS methodology and was based on [HadCRUT v5.0.2.0](#).

8.3 What are the geographies?

The Recent Heat Packs provide local information for all UK local authorities at District level and above. In England that includes county councils, district councils, unitary authorities, metropolitan districts, London boroughs, combined authorities. The set of 393 local authorities are those for which the Local Authority Climate Service was launched. Subsequent changes to the UK's administrative geography have not been incorporated into this prototype product.

Many may find it useful to have climate information at smaller spatial scales than the local authority. The Recent Heat Packs supply this for the census areas ('MSOA level') that nest within the local authority area: MSOAs in England and Wales, Intermediate Zones in Scotland, and District Electoral Areas in Northern Ireland.

It is legitimate to combine climate information at MSOA level with other information on finer spatial scales, such as census-based information at LSOA level (LSOAs in England and Wales, Data Zones in Scotland, Super Data Zones in Northern Ireland). The Data Summary Product information at MSOA level may be applied to all the LSOA shapes within an MSOA.

8.4 How do the numbers align to the Local Authority Climate Service?

The Recent Heat Packs provide the temperatures **observed** in **2013-2024**. The Local Authority Climate Service (LACS) provides **modelled** temperatures from a number of periods, including 1981-2000, 2001-2020, and some future periods. As such, no like-for-like comparison is possible.

However, the Global Warming Level reached in 2013-2024 was 1.2°C, which falls approximately halfway between the 2001-2020 (1°C) period and the 1.5°C future period in the LACS. So, it is reasonable to compare the Recent Heat Packs and these two periods in the LACS. For many areas and metrics the values are similar, compared to the difference with 1981-2000 (0.6°C) or higher Global Warming Levels such as 4°C. Where there are differences, these are due primarily to LACS providing model-based information, but also because of the natural variability of climate, and because of the uncertainties arising from the inevitably partial nature of the observed record.

It is legitimate to use the information in the Recent Heat Factsheets to complement the LACS. For example, the temperature metrics in the LACS tell a story of increasing local temperatures as the climate warms, from 1981-2000 to a 4°C world. The Recent Heat Factsheets show the temperatures that have been reached locally in a world that has warmed by 1.2°C.

It is also legitimate to use the finer spatial information in the Recent Heat Packs to complement the LACS. The Recent Heat Packs show how temperatures have varied across the local authority area in the recent past. It is likely that the sub-local authority areas that have experienced the hottest temperatures in the recent past will also experience them in the future, unless changes to the local

environment alter the pattern of heat. It is legitimate to combine that information with information about exposure and vulnerability to assess relative risk across a local authority area.

9. Further Resources & Acknowledgements

- [Feedback & Enquiries](#) - This is a prototype; your feedback is welcome.
- [Crowd-Grid](#) – The Crowd-Grid dataset on CEDA
- [Recent Heat Packs](#) – The Recent Heat Packs dataset on CEDA
- [HadUK-Grid Information](#) - Complementary dataset to Crowd-Grid (used by Met Office for UK climate monitoring statistics)
- [HadUK-Grid Data](#) - Link to HadUK-Grid collection on CEDA
- [Local Authority Climate Service](#) - Further information regarding the Met Office's Local Authority Climate Service (LACS)
- [LACS Scientific Detail](#) - Further technical detail regarding the scientific basis of the LACS
- [WOW](#) - Met Office platform for citizen science observations
- [UK Observations Network](#) - Information about Met Office land observation network

Acknowledgement is given to National Highways, Transport Scotland, and Department for Infrastructure (NI), in addition to the volunteers and users of the Met Office WOW service, for the provision of data used in the generation of Crowd-Grid.

10. Licence & Copyright

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